

A Comparative Testing of Viscosity Equations Recommended for Concentrated Aqueous Solutions

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A comparative testing of the viscosity equations of Vand, Thomas and the author has been made, in detail, for electrolyte and non electrolyte solutions at 25°. It has been observed that Thomas' equation, in its full form, is not applicable for majority cases. The equation of Vand is a better relation. The calculated molar volume (\bar{V}) values and the B coefficients bear the simple relation $B = 2.5 \bar{V}$. A single viscosity equation may not be sufficient to cover the viscosity data of most aqueous systems containing high fractions of dissolved solutes. The parameters of the equations have been evaluated and recorded. These may be used to calculate viscosity of aqueous solutions in the concentration range in which an equation is valid.

The viscosity equation of Einstein¹ and Jones and Dole² are applicable to dilute solutions.

$$\text{Einstein :} \quad \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + 2.5\phi \quad \dots (1)$$

where, $\frac{\eta}{\eta_0}$ and ϕ represent the solution and solvent viscosity ratio, and the volume fraction of the dissolved solute.

$$\text{Jones and Dole :} \quad \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + A\sqrt{c} + Bc \quad \dots (2)$$

where, A and B are the long range interparticle (interionic) interaction coefficient and the solute-solvent interaction coefficient respectively, and c is the concentration of the solute in moles lit⁻¹.

It is known that at concentration $\geq 0.1 M$, B swamps out the effect of A , and equation (3) results.

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + Bc = 1 + \frac{B}{\bar{V}} \phi \quad \dots (3)$$

(since $\phi = \bar{V}c$, where, \bar{V} is the molar volume of the solute in lit mole⁻¹).

Though the picture of viscosity is not very complex for dilute solutions, at concentrations above $0.1M$, representation of viscosity by one general equation is very difficult. Several equations have been put forward in this direction³⁻⁶.

$$\text{Vand :} \quad \ln \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = \frac{2.5 \phi}{1 - Q\phi} \quad \dots (4)$$

where, Q is the interaction coefficient.

$$\text{Thomas :} \quad \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + 2.5\phi + 10.05\phi^2 \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\text{Moulik :} \quad \left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0}\right)^2 = M + K'c^2 \quad \dots (6)$$

where, M and K' are constants.

The above equations though have been tested for only limited systems, a comparative study, as to the general validity and the range of concentration in which they are actually valid, has not been made. Results of such an investigation have been discussed in this paper. It can be emphasized that a direct testing of Thomas' equation in the case of electrolyte solution has not been made in the past.

Procedure of testing : It can be seen from the equations (4), (5) and (6) that viscosity cannot be calculated without having knowledge of the constants, Q , M and K' . The up-to-date knowledge does not permit to evaluate them theoretically. Therefore, graphical testing is the only other alternative of proving. This has been performed in the present work. This will evaluate the values of Q , M , K' and \bar{V} , which once known can be useful to calculate the solution viscosity. In doing this, data have been collected from literature⁷⁻⁹ for these electrolytes and non electrolytes which give viscosity values for at least four concentrations above $0.1M$ at 25° .

The equations of Vand and Thomas have been rearranged in the linear forms and used.

$$\text{Vand :} \quad \frac{1}{c} = \left(\frac{0.921}{\bar{V}}\right) \frac{1}{\log \frac{\eta}{\eta_0}} + Q\bar{V} \quad \dots (7)$$

$$\text{Thomas :} \quad \left(\frac{\eta - 1}{\eta_0 c}\right) = 2.5\bar{V} + (10.05\bar{V}^2)c \quad \dots (8)$$

Plots of $1/c$ vs. $1/\log \frac{\eta}{\eta_0}$ for equation 7, $\left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1\right)/c$ vs c for equation (8), and $\left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0}\right)^2$ vs c^2 for equation (6) have been made and linearity of these results has been tested. The results of 40 solutes are given in Table 1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Table 1 the B coefficients of the electrolytes¹⁰ are also listed. As to the validity of the equations, it is seen that of the 35 electrolytes, 25 hold the equation of Vand, 19 hold the equation of Thomas, and 27 hold the equation 6. Results of only (7) non electrolytes are given, of which 4 hold equation (7), 2 hold equation (8) and 3 hold equation (6). This observation is of course based on the fact so far as the linearity of the plots are concerned. An important logical conclusion can be that the relations (6), (7) and (8) have more or less similar, if not equal, probability of fitting the experimental data. But the concentration limit into which these relations hold may be different.

TABLE I
Vand's Eqn. Thomas' Eqn. Eqn. 6

Solute	Tested conc. limit		Vand's Eqn.		Thomas' Eqn.		Eqn. 6		Ref.				
	M or F/l	M or F/l	Valid zone M or F/l	Q lit. mol ⁻¹	Valid zone M or F/l	Intercept lit. mol ⁻¹	\bar{V} lit. mol ⁻¹	Valid zone M or F/l		M	K'	B	
AgNO ₃	3.0-9.6	5.0-9.6	5.0-9.6	0.886	0.0345	3.0-6.2	0.035	0.041	13.92	3.0-5.2	0.071	0.045	7
C ₃ H ₅ NH ₃ Cl	0.1-7.0	N _h	N _h	—	—	N _h	—	—	—	0.25-7.0	2.06	0.319	8
BaCl ₂	0.1-1.0	0.25-1.0	0.25-1.0	0.509	0.098	N _h	—	—	—	0.25-1.0	0.21	0.041	7
Ca(NO ₃) ₂	0.1-3.0	0.1-2.0	0.1-2.0	3.886	0.077	0.1-3.0	0.076	0.014	16.89	0.1-3.0	0.542	0.193	8
CuCl ₂	0.1-3.0	0.1-3.0	0.1-3.0	0.337	0.148	0.1-3.0	0.158	0.063	1.82	0.25-3.0	0.565	0.371	8
CuSO ₄	0.1-1.0	0.1-1.0	0.1-1.0	0.641	0.234	0.1-1.0	0.228	0.174	5.57	0.1-1.0	2.27	0.594	8
FeCl ₃	0.05-4.7	0.1-4.7	0.1-4.7	0.200	0.258	0.5-2.0	0.252	0.150	3.38	0.1-2.0	2.25	0.740	8
HBr	0.25-3.0	N _h	N _h	—	—	N _h	—	—	—	N _h	—	0.027	8
HCl	0.2-16.0	1.0-11.0	1.0-11.0	0	0.026	8.0-16.0	0.022	0.034	22.30	4.0-16.0	0.012	0.062	8
KCl	1.5-4.0	N _h	N _h	—	—	N _h	—	—	—	N _h	—	0.014	7
K ₂ CrO ₄	0.2-2.5	0.2-2.5	0.2-2.5	3.62	0.014	1.0-2.5	0.058	0.008	3.28	0.25-2.5	0.34	—	7
K ₂ CrO ₄	0.53-6.5	0.53-6.5	0.53-6.5	0.113	0.049	N _h	—	—	—	0.53-6.0	0.096	0.113	7
K ₂ Fe(CN) ₆	0.1-1.2	0.1-1.0	0.1-1.0	2.713	0.074	N _h	—	—	—	0.1-1.2	0.775	0.117	7
KOH	0.1-2.0	0.1-2.0	0.1-2.0	0	0.048	0.1-2.0	0.049	0.024	2.47	0.25-2.0	0.135	0.102	8
K ₂ SO ₄	0.1-0.5	0.1-0.5	0.1-0.5	2.553	0.783	N _h	—	—	—	N _h	—	0.195	7
LaCl ₃	0.1-1.0	0.1-1.0	0.1-1.0	0.447	0.224	0.1-1.0	0.224	0.170	5.79	0.1-1.0	2.220	0.567	7
LiCl	0.4-4.0	0.4-4.0	0.4-4.0	0.214	0.056	0.7-3.5	0.056	0.034	3.71	0.7-4.0	0.119	0.140	7
LiClO ₃	0.5-7.2	0.9-7.2	0.9-7.2	0.714	0.047	0.9-3.7	0.056	0.040	7.19	0.5-5.2	0.118	0.126	7
LiNO ₃	0.1-13.6	1.0-9.1	1.0-9.1	1.106	0.039	0.8-6.0	0.038	0.036	8.51	0.1-6.0	0.097	0.101	7
MgCl ₂	0.05-3.0	0.05-2.0	0.05-2.0	1.147	0.131	0.1-2.0	0.130	0.121	8.51	0.1-2.0	0.20	0.096	8
MgSO ₄	0.05-2.0	0.05-1.0	0.05-1.0	1.000	0.230	0.1-2.0	0.230	0.189	6.82	0.1-1.0	2.510	0.594	8
MnCl ₂	0.1-3.0	0.1-3.0	0.1-3.0	0.671	0.149	0.1-1.0	0.149	0.086	3.84	0.25-3.0	0.810	0.420	7
N(CH ₃) ₄ Br	0.01-1.0	N _h	N _h	—	—	N _h	—	—	—	N _h	—	—	8
NaBr	0.3-7.0	N _h	N _h	—	—	N _h	—	—	—	0.3-4.5	0.070	0.044%	7
NaCl	0.1-5.0	0.5-5.0	0.5-5.0	0.141	0.034	N _h	—	—	—	0.5-5.0	0.069	0.079	9
NaClO ₄	0.5-9.0	N _h	N _h	—	—	N _h	—	—	—	0.5-3.0	0.081	0.006	9
NaCN	0.5-9.0	N _h	N _h	—	—	N _h	—	—	—	0.5-4.0	0.081	—	9
NaF	0.1-9.0	0.1-0.9	0.1-0.9	0	0.083	N _h	—	—	—	N _h	—	—	7
NaNO ₂	0.1-7.0	4.0-7.0	4.0-7.0	0.115	0.034	0.1-7.0	0.043	0.048	12.27	0.5-5.0	0.082	0.040	10
Na ₂ SO ₄	0.2-2.0	0.07-2.0	0.07-2.0	0.368	0.163	0.2-0.8	0.163	0.107	4.32	0.3-2.0	1.765	0.371	7
NH ₄ NO ₃	4.0-11.1	N _h	N _h	—	—	N _h	—	—	—	N _h	—	0.053	7
NH ₄ OH	0.25-13.0	N _h	N _h	—	—	N _h	—	—	—	N _h	—	-0.053	8
N(CH ₃) ₃ Br	0.01-1.04	N _h	N _h	—	—	N _h	—	—	—	N _h	—	—	8
Pb(NO ₃) ₂	0.1-1.5	0.1-1.5	0.1-1.5	3.546	0.071	0.5-1.5	0.060	0.009	18.41	0.1-1.5	0.500	0.029	8
SrCl ₂	0.1-3.0	0.1-3.0	0.1-3.0	1.064	0.097	0.1-2.0	0.102	0.086	7.96	0.25-3.0	0.587	—	8
Acetamide	0.1-1.0	N _h	N _h	—	—	N _h	—	—	—	N _h	—	—	8
Dextrose	0.1-1.0	0.1-1.0	0.1-1.0	0.826	0.182	N _h	—	—	—	0.5-1.0	1.020	—	8
Propionic acid	0.1-2.0	0.1-2.0	0.1-2.0	0	0.074	0.1-2.0	0.078	0.038	5.70	N _h	—	—	8
Propionamide	0.2-9.7	0.2-9.7	0.2-9.7	0.695	0.072	0.2-3.0	0.070	0.0025	4.82	0.7-3.0	0.200	—	8
Sucrose	0.3-1.8	0.3-1.8	0.3-1.8	1.041	0.336	N _h	—	—	—	N _h	—	—	8
Urea	0.2-7.7	N _h	N _h	—	—	N _h	—	—	—	1.4-7.7	1.033	0.030	8
Urea (30°)	2.0-9.44	N _h	N _h	—	—	N _h	—	—	—	2.0-9.44	1.08	0.028	5

M = molarity; F/l = formula wt/litre; N_h = not holds; K_S = K_{solute}

We shall now discuss a comparison between the equations of Vand and Thomas from the \bar{V} point of view. It is seen that in relations (7) and (8) both the intercept and the slope yield the value of \bar{V} . An advantage of equation (8) is that since both the intercept and the slope contain only this effective rigid molar volume as the unknown term, therefore, obtaining identical value from these two sources must be a condition for the true fitting of this equation with the viscosity data. Unfortunately, it has been observed that except for the electrolytes, MgCl_2 , NaNO_3 , AgNO_3 and LiNO_3 , the \bar{V} values obtained from the intercept and from the slope are not even nearly equal. The slope emerging values are significantly lower than the intercept emerging values. This makes the impression that Thomas equation, in its full form, is not valid for electrolytes, and may not be valid also for many non electrolytes. However, a remarkable feature of the intercept constituting \bar{V} values is that they are very close to those obtained from the linear equation of Vand. This forces us to believe that the equation of Vand holds in a far better way, and it appears that the constant part of the second term of Thomas equation may not be 10.05 for all the systems. It varies from one solute

$$\frac{\left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1\right)}{c} = 2.5\bar{V} + (K_{\text{solute}}\bar{V}^2)c \quad \dots (10)$$

where, $K_{\text{solute}} = \frac{\text{slope}}{\bar{V}^2}$. The highest and the lowest value of K_{solute} have been observed to be 22.30 (HCl) and 1.82 (CaCl_2) respectively.

In a recent paper Breslau and Miller¹⁰ have attempted to give a procedure of calculating the viscosity of concentrated aqueous solutions of electrolytes at 25° from a knowledge of the B coefficients. They have attempted empirically and reached at different relations between B and \bar{V} depending on the valency of the electrolytes.

$$\text{Univalent electrolyte : } B = 2.79\bar{V} - 0.018 \quad \dots (11)$$

$$\text{Bivalent electrolyte : } B = 6.65\bar{V} - 0.0416 \quad \dots (12)$$

To evaluate the \bar{V} values they have solved the quadratic equation of Thomas assuming that it holds for almost all electrolytes at concentrations above 0.1M. From what has been discussed above it can be remarked that this is a risky procedure. A mathematical solution of Thomas equation for \bar{V} , without any direct testing of its validity may calculate values (cf. Table 1) which may not be true. Relations of the types (11) and (12) are, therefore, not surprising. To check the validity of the relations (11) and (12), the B values have been plotted against the presently obtained \bar{V} values (Fig. 1). A line equivalent to the relation $B = 2.5\bar{V}$ [(cf. equations (1) and (2))] adequately fits the data irrespective of the valency of the electrolytes. It should be mentioned in this connection that equation (6) cannot be brought under such a comparison because the constants M and K' are not yet defined. Only the values obtained for them are given in Table 1.

A look into the table will also reveal the concentration ranges in which the equations are valid. The range of concentration may be the same or different. As typical examples, calculated viscosity values using the constants of the equations, have been compared with the experimented values for a few solutes (Fig. 2). The working domains of different equations can be readily seen.

Fig. 1. B vs \bar{V} plot for electrolytes.
 Line A : Drawn according to equation 12.
 Line B : Drawn according to equation 11.
 Line C : Drawn according to equation $B = 2.5\bar{V}$.
 Signs : ● monovalent electrolyte
 ○ bivalent electrolyte
 ⊙ trivalent electrolyte.

Fig. 2. Variation of relative viscosity with concentration. Lines are theoretically drawn points and are experimentally obtained.
 FeCl_3 : A : Vand; B : Thomas; C : Moulik.
 Urea : D : Moulik (r.s. ordinate)
 LiNO_3 : E : Vand; F : Thomas; G : Moulik.

The constants Q , K_{solute} , and K' have been tried to relate with either \bar{V} or B . It has been apparently seen that there can be relations among K' , \bar{V} and B . This will be reported elsewhere. It appears that most probably Q and K_{solute} are specific properties of a solute. They are not general properties.

In conclusion it can be said that, at this stage, all the viscosity equations (6), (7) and (10) may be necessary to compute viscosity of concentrated solutions, but only in the concentration ranges in which they are valid.

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